

Session #1

Collaboration Issues & Tool Frictions

✓ 1
sedentariness: needing to be at 'good' wfl. there is this idea that we are 'mobile' because of online collab tools, but its not true — we have to be near a good connection, and in a kind of 'appropriate environment' for a meeting / call. online / time at the screen. maybe an obvious repercussion, but our legs/back/eyes are suffering. forced / timed breaks? exercises and outside time etc. (jamie)

✓ 1
Tension between the impulse to disconnect and the necessity to stay connected

✓ 1
Michael: issue of "offline" information about changes/updates in a shared document, when using it a group, but not at all the time at the same time

✓ 1
Zoom meetings not only to discuss/solve/negotiate things/problems
it would be nice to discover things together - zoom journey, collective museum tour
it seems often that zoom meetings are the extended form of frontal teaching

✓ 1
the impoverishment of acoustic and visual 'space', as part of relations and experience of collaboration. everything and everyone sounds and feels like it has the same 'dimension', no big rooms, small rooms, intimate or 'loud' spaces
Also: how best to hold space when there is no space (jamie)

✓ 1
head-shots: something about the way people look on these interfaces, camera placement, the psychology of everyone 'looking down their noses' at one another (jamie)
<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/look%20down%20one%27s%20nose%20at>

✓ 1
Issue: Unshared Spaces (also: headspace) - how can we attune to each other?

✓ 1
digital leftovers
Collections of Links/Leftovers of meetings / losing overview

✓ 1
schedule and deadline formality / informality. there is a lot of 'sliding around' of meetings because of the disappearance / 'convenience' of geographies. similarly i find deadlines, as everything transpires online, to be a bit less 'concrete' when things are negotiated solely online. i'm not sure if i like this or don't like this (jamie)

✓ 1
tool packages
each collaboration requires a different 'tool package' (usually combining 2-3-4 different apps and online tools), often you need to login with a different institutional account for each, search emails to find links to the latest docs, etc.
nightmare to remember and keep track
Whirlpool = great solution?
sharing 'tool packages' with different teams, with a set of internal rules & agreements of participants

✓ 1
it's cold in here (jamie)

✓ 1
common attentions — trusting that someone is 'paying attention' and being able to signal that i am paying attention despite the 'small' presences available (jamie)

✓ 1
awkward silence in zoom sessions

✓ 1
JONAS
PHYSICAL DISCONNECTION

✓ 1
Communicative qualifiers (e.g. how to signal urgency; how to communicate intentions; etc.)

✓ 1
de-personalising and de-sensitising work - making things more relativised, fun, open and less 'anxious' and 'touchy'. somehow a good umber of online interactions and tools make everything very very serious and even divisive... hard to be informal / fun / funny / poetic / beautiful ... relates to motivation, desire, etc. (jamie)

✓ 1
missing comfort
lack of feedback

✓ 1
concentration problems
rules and non rules of online meetings
disconnection from the "real"

✓ 1
overcome productivity

✓ 1
hanging out. (jamie)

✓ 1
collectively collecting pop up associations

✓ 1
How to disagree productively?
(JONAS)

✓ 1
RE-DEFINING "PRIVACY" (in the light of ubiquitous computing)
(JONAS)

✓ 1
tool fatigue, learning new collaborative tools, having someone tell me about some new tool that we should all be using. feeling like i need to sign up / know about / use every tool (jamie)
p.s.: e.g. i signed up for Craft during this session because Moritz was using it

✓ 1
people are used to __different tools__ and it's hard to introduce new ones or __new conventions/habits__ in general

✓ 1
tension between manifesting structure and queering it/keeping it dynamic

✓ 1
interesting example
Care Rider (for research collaborations)
(discussing and acknowledging different practical and mental needs of collaborators, setting and respecting the terms.)
hosting

✓ 1
General well-being
(JONAS)

✓ 1
shared contexts — the initiation of trust and communication as transpiring through (Goffman esque?) frames like 'funny weather we are having, no', or other things about the room, time of day, clothing, etc. that would normally situate everyone in the 'same space' (physically but also cognitively, emotionally) (jamie)

✓ 1
How to establish common ground (both literally and metaphorically)?

✓ 1
PROCESS DOCUMENTATION
I feel that the on-boarding process in tools such as micro, or Werkbank is sometimes difficult. So, if you missed one session, it's hard to orient yourself, unless, there's some type of "metadata" informing you about the process.
There's often a lack of documentation of processes helping others to get in.

✓ 1
there's often a gap between people's intentions to commit to collaborative formats and the actual participation - which is a systemic issue, not an individual shortcoming

✓ 1
taking care of collaboration takes a lot of time and effort that is often not planned for within project work packages

✓ 1
Status
Abfall/nicht Abfall
Responsibility for parts of a document
Version History
Timeliness
"Zeitvergessenheit" der Tools

✓ 1
tools have tutorials but collaboration doesn't

✓ 1
Before setting up common codes; encountering issues of over-stepping / writing-over / understanding how to demonstrate respect for the other's work while making space for oneself on the tool (like a shared google doc) or the balance between presence and giving space for the other's presence.

✓ 1
navigating hard and soft coded power structures

Session #2

New Formats

Group 2:

Moritz, Lucie, Michael

Issue

How to make a process traceable and interoperable?

Could the issue be generalized?

Do tools for collaboration offer all needed features or are they just an expansion of single-user tools for several users? Do the tools especially support specific practices (like XYZ) of collaborative work?

How would you deal with it now? What tools or processes?

define different lines of action
- temporality, categorization etc. (in comments for example, where you get to say something about the status of your contribution to a document)
- interplay of online and offline activities

What would be a novel format to address the issue?

eg. KOM
(<https://azi.kleio.com/record/work/81>) or
gitHub-inspired tools such as Abstract
(<https://www.abstract.com/2021-archive/notebooks>).

Group 3:

Merle, Joseph, Johannes

Issue

Meeting in/formalities

Could the issue be generalized?

Breaking up the Zoom / Meeting

How would you deal with it now? What tools or processes?

- Code of (in)formalities for specific kinds of meetings
- define purpose of meetings
- adjust format of the meetings accordingly
- break meetings up into parts (even more)

What would be a novel format to address the issue?

- Team Meeting --> WG Meeting
- code of consent

Group 4:

Jamie, Jonas, Felix

Issue:

missing shared context

Could the issue be generalized?

sharing NEW norms
in terms of what we feel, do and don't do

How would you deal with it now? What tools or processes?

- routines to expose context, e.g. at the beginning of a meeting

What would be a novel format to address the issue?

a special meeting regularly that is 'about' context (or sharing context, 'ice cream' sessions...)

a 'context'

Issue

tool inertia/fatigue

How would you deal with it now? What tools or processes?

meta-data and information about seemingly 'unimportant' stuff...

pasting the weather in the chat at the beginning of a call

tool that keeps you interested/excited: off-topic channels, social media-like streams, being able to mess with the environment (including Zoom background switching, filters etc.?)

find a way to keep and express joy

Could the issue be generalized?

general reduction in stuff that we do

do things more consciously

sleep more

What would be a novel format to address the issue?

heads up displays that give 'context', mood...

click-engagement / movement engagement (real time likes)

attention - feedback - 'keep alive' techniques?

Group 6:

Anastasia, Flavia, Solveig

Issue

How to set-up a common ground?
The onboarding process

Could the issue be generalized?

How to involve group members and set up the workflow?

How would you deal with it now? What tools or processes?

Informal chat on needs & expectations & rhythms of work & restrictions & conditions

Sharing of personal processes

Continual social check-ins

What would be a novel format to address the issue?

Test out different working flows:
according to lunar calendar // cosmic energy